

18 months of the SPATIAL project

18 months ago, 12 partners from 8 EU countries, led by TU Delft, set out on an ambitious mission to establish a trustworthy European cybersecurity sector. The goal was to create a reliable governance and regulatory framework for AI-driven security in Europe.

[Learn about the SPATIALS results](#)

SPATIAL interviews!

In February, we attended the SPATIAL consortium meeting hosted by Telefónica in Barcelona, where we had the fantastic opportunity to interview several consortium partners. We're excited to announce that we now have published the interviews with the coordinators, which provide an in-depth look at the project and its many achievements.

[Watch the interviews](#)

SPATIAL publications

Explore the SPATIAL scientific publications to gain deeper insights into the accomplishments and key milestones of this project.

Why are women important in AI?

Within the project, we are proud to be working with many women, some of them in scientific positions working on artificial intelligence.

Joint cybersecurity workshop

This workshop provided an overview of how novel solutions can protect the ICT infrastructures and create a more innovative and resilient European industry.

Our Collaborators!

Discover more about the exciting projects we're collaborating with! We are constantly seeking out new partnerships and collaborations to further our mission, and we're thrilled to be working with a range of innovative initiatives that are making a real difference in the AI and cybersecurity world.

Collaborators' news

Coming soon!

Exciting news! Get ready to tune in because we've got some amazing podcast series coming soon! Stay tuned for entertaining and informative episodes that cover a wide range of topics related to trustworthy AI. We can't wait to share these podcast series with you!

SPATIAL

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